

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Project Number: 823782

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 40 months

Deliverable 8.1 Governance and Sustainability Roadmap

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	28/02/2022 (M38)
Actual Submission Date	29/04/2022
Work Package	WP8 - Governance/ Sustainability/ Quality Assurance
Task	Task 8.1 Governance & Sustainability
Type	Report
Approval Status	Approved by EC- 04 May 2022)
Version	v1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.28

Abstract:

This report provides an overview of the post-project agreements and steps prepared in view of the future governance of the services developed and improved as a result of the SSHOC project.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
0.0	29/07/2021	draft creation	Franciska de Jong
0.1	19/10/2021	ToC refinement	Franciska de Jong
0.2	25/10/2021	Addition annexes	Franciska de Jong
0.3	15/11/2021	Addition section 1.1	Franciska de Jong, Leon Wessels, Karina Berger
0.4	29/01/2021	Input from consortium members (e.g. LIBER) processed	Franciska de Jong
0.5	21/04/2022	Included: details on MoU and KERs	Franciska de Jong
0.6	23/04/2022	Polishing structure and ToC; reducing number of annexes	Franciska de Jong
0.7	23/04/2022	Polishing	Franciska de Jong
0.8	28/04/2022	Input and revision after coordinator comments	Franciska de Jong
1.0	29/04/2022	Version for submission	Martina Drascic Capar, Ivana Ilijasic Versic

Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
CLARIN ERIC	Franciska de Jong	f.m.g.dejong@uu.nl
CLARIN ERIC	Leon Wessels	leon@clarin.eu
CLARIN ERIC	Karina Berger	karina.berger@clarin.eu
CLARIN ERIC	Daan Broeder	d.g.broeder@uu.nl

Executive Summary

This deliverable D8.1 addresses (i) the organisational structure needed to safeguard the availability, quality and maintenance of the results after the SSHOC project, (ii) the conditions for financial sustainability of the exploitable results and (iii) the actions needed to implement and sustain the envisaged organisational structure for the post-project collaboration and sustainability. It provides an overview of the post-project agreements regarding the model for the sustained collaboration under the umbrella *SSH Open Cluster*, as well as the agreements and steps prepared in view of the future governance of the services developed and improved as a result of the SSHOC project.

The SSH Open Cluster launched in April as the umbrella organisation for the European research infrastructures (RIs) in the social science and humanities (SSH) is the main instrument for safeguarding the sustainability of the results of the SSHOC project and for promoting quality and impact of SSH through the model of a federated service offer and know-how sharing in all areas of common interest with strong involvement of the different SSH community stakeholders. At the same time the cluster will actively continue to act as one of the thematic pillars for the role of science clusters in the EOSC landscape and the wider RI ecosystem. The common planning of activities and the further development of models capturing the commitment needed to realise this ambition are included in the Roadmap presented. Some of the ingredients for this Roadmap, such as the MoU signed by the RIs involved, the charter for the SSH Vocabulary Commons, an overview of services onboarded in EOSC Portal and the governance model for the SSH Open Marketplace, all prepared in the context of the SSHOC project, are introduced in some more detail.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESS	European Social Survey
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
RI	Research Infrastructure
SHARE	European Research Infrastructure Consortium for the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
TDM	Text and Data Mining
ToR	Terms of Reference

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
1.1 The Value of a Sustained RI Service Offer for SSH	6
1.2 Purpose and approach underlying this report	8
1.3 Structure of the document	9
2. Roadmap Ingredients	10
2.1 Introduction	10
2.2 Exploitable Results	11
2.2.1 33 KERs	11
2.2.2 SSHOC Open Marketplace	11
2.2.3 Services onboarded in EOSC Portal	12
2.3 Memorandum of Understanding	13
2.4 Future Surveys: Potential Topics	13
3. Roadmap	15
3.1 Actions/Tasks	15
3.1.1 Coordinated ongoing tasks	15
3.1.3 Specific tasks	15
3.1.3 Tasks for individual RIs	16
3.2 Timeline	16
4. Concluding Remarks	18
5. References	19
Annex 1 - 33 Key Exploitable Results	22
Annex 2 - ToR Governing Board SSH Open Marketplace	23
Annex 3 - Potential Survey Topic List	26
Annex 4 - SSH Vocabulary Commons Charter	28

1. Introduction

In the Description of Action of the SSHOC project this deliverable D8.1 was envisaged to identify (i) the organisational structure needed to safeguard the availability, quality and maintenance of the results after the SSHOC project, (ii) the conditions for financial sustainability of the exploitable results and (iii) the actions needed to implement and sustain the envisaged organisational structure for the post-project collaboration and sustainability.

At the end of project, the objectives for the project task T8.1 Governance and Sustainability, in the context of which D8.1 has been prepared, has led to the launch of the SSH Open Cluster as the umbrella organisation for the European research infrastructures (RIs) in the social science and humanities (SSH). It will be the main instrument for safeguarding the sustainability of the results of the SSHOC project and for promoting quality and impact of SSH through the model of a federated service offer and know-how sharing in all areas of common interest with strong involvement of the different SSH community stakeholders. At the same time the cluster will actively continue to act as one of the thematic pillars for the role of science clusters in the wider RI ecosystem. The common planning and commitment needed to realise this ambition are captured in this Roadmap.

For this deliverable, information has been aggregated from all project Work Packages. Some of the topics covered in this deliverable are also covered by the end-of-project legacy booklet¹ that was launched during the final project conference (6-7 April 2022).

1.1 The Value of a Sustained RI Service Offer for SSH

Scientific breakthroughs can rarely be attributed to a single individual. They call for bright minds with different expertises and easy access to resources. To facilitate platforms for researchers, industry, and citizen-scientists from various backgrounds to collaborate and find the data and technology they need to succeed, Europe has designed a vast landscape of research infrastructures. These research infrastructures are key to Europe's capacity 'to deliver scientific breakthroughs and foster innovation'.² Within the context of SSHOC, the next phase in the European integration of research and innovation has been explored: the setting up of a thematic science cluster of research infrastructures in the broad domain of the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). As an introduction to Deliverable 8.1, this section presents some notes on the added value of science clusters.

¹ SSHOC. (2022). SSHOC Legacy booklet. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6394462>

² Making Science Happen. ESFRI White Paper 2020; link: https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/White_paper_ESFRI-final.pdf (accessed April 2022)

First of all, science clusters are an excellent way to create synergy among research infrastructures. As acknowledged by the High-Level Expert Group (HLEG), which assessed the progress of ESFRI and other world class research infrastructures towards the implementation and long-term sustainability set up by the European Commission, establishing science clusters strengthens the overall impact of Research Infrastructures and increases their efficiency.³ Within such clusters, research infrastructures can collaborate on achieving the goal of Open Science in practice. Together, research infrastructures can better promote the adoption of common standards and formats such as the FAIR data principles.

In addition, science clusters enable Europe to respond to societal challenges faster and more cohesively. Addressing complex issues such as climate change, pandemics, social injustice, migration, and multilinguality requires a coordinated, multifaceted approach. Research infrastructures have demonstrated their important role in addressing the challenges of today's social and cultural dynamics; their contributions to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals serve as just one example.⁴ By fostering collaboration and interoperability, and at the same time recognising the fact that RIs may implement certain infrastructural services in domain-specific ways, science clusters support multidisciplinary approaches and increase the overall readiness of Europe to respond to challenges.⁵

Moreover, science clusters and their focus on thematic (as opposed to generic) services are essential for the successful implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). As an emerging initiative to establish a 'web of FAIR Data and services for Science in Europe', EOSC builds on existing frameworks and service federation initiatives such as research infrastructures. For EOSC to succeed, the 'thematic clustering of research infrastructures, e-infrastructure and regional projects is seen as a critical first step'.⁶ Science clusters occupy a unique position between the EOSC and research infrastructures: they are the linking pins connecting the EOSC with research infrastructures, which provide thematic services and have established communication channels with end-users.⁷

³ Supporting the Transformative Impact of Research Infrastructures on European Research (HLEG report 2020); link:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/supporting-transformative-impact-research-infrastructures-european-research_en (Accessed April 2022)

⁴ How ERICs Contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals; link:

<https://www.eric-forum.eu/2021/10/11/erics-contribution-to-the-un-sustainable-development-goals-sdgs/> (Accessed April 2022)

⁵ ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement, June 2021; link:

<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-science-clusters-position-statement-expectations-and-long-term-commitment-open-science> (Accessed April 2022)

⁶ Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC. A FAIR Lady report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group; link: <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/solutions-sustainable-eosc-fair-lady-report> (Accessed April 2022)

⁷ Assessment on the Implementation of the ERIC Regulation (draft 31/08/2021); link:

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/cdbe5c78-353b-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> (Accessed April 2022)

Figure 1. The five science cluster projects that received funding under H2020 INFRAEOSC-04-2018 call are: EOSC-Life, ENVRI FAIR, ESCAPE, PaNOSC, and SSHOC.

In the context described above, science clusters have become an important new element in the European Research Area policy agenda^{8, 9} and they are seen as key enablers of important scientific breakthroughs in the future. The SSHOC consortium has proven that research infrastructures in the SSH domain can jointly provide a valuable service offer. In the remainder of this deliverable, a roadmap will be presented to ensure the governance of this joint service offer as part of a sustained collaboration within the SSH cluster.

1.2 Purpose and approach underlying this report

As mentioned D8.1 was envisaged to identify (i) the organisational structure needed to safeguard the availability, quality and maintenance of the results after the SSHOC project, (ii) the conditions for financial sustainability of the exploitable results and (iii) the actions needed to implement and sustain the envisaged organisational structure for the post-project collaboration and sustainability. The results and follow-up plans for each of the three topics are summarised based on information that has been aggregated from input stemming from all project Work Packages as well as external consultations.

⁸ European Research Area Policy Agenda (2022 – 2024); November 2021;

link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/files/european-research-area-policy-agenda-2022-2024_en (Accessed April 2022)

⁹ Research infrastructures look to renew their role in new-look European Research Area. In: Science | Business; published 22 July 2021; link:

<https://sciencebusiness.net/news/research-infrastructures-look-renew-their-role-new-look-european-research-area> (Accessed April 2022)

The methodology followed for collecting the relevant information included the following:

- Check of relevant policy documents, such as those of EOSC Working Groups, e.g. the Fair Lady report, and the ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement (cf. footnote 4).
- Internal and external feedback rounds, organised through both formal and weekly structured exchange formats in order to reach consent on the various agreement templates and models developed for the governance and support of the post-project activities.
- Feedback collection from a wide network of experts through formal and informal channels for a number of topics, a.o.:
 - Insights into the relation between the governance and sustainability of EOSC on the one hand and the thematic service offer of the science clusters on the other hand
 - Drafts of the MoU for the collaboration of the lead beneficiaries of SSHOC towards the establishment of the SSH Open Cluster and the wider SSH community (see section 2.3)
 - Terms of reference for the Governing Board envisaged for the SSH Open Marketplace (as described in D7.5 Marketplace - Governance; see section 2.2.2 and the summary in Annex 2)
 - Suggestions for case studies that can attract new categories of users.
 - Options for post-project measuring of service quality.

In addition to an overview of the identified elements/instruments for ensuring the post-project sustainability, the deliverable will present a roadmap for the various stages and activities in the process of safeguarding the project results in the first years after the project.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is organised into three sections. After this introductory chapter the main ingredients for the Governance and Sustainability Roadmap will be presented in Section 2, while in Section 3 a more detailed overview of actions envisaged for the post-project period is presented. Some annexes are added as well.

2. Roadmap Ingredients

2.1 Introduction

SSHOC has led to a number of project results that will play a crucial role in the afterlife of the project and the action lines that the SSH Open Cluster will undertake to ensure a sustained role for the RI cluster targeting the various communities of use and data communities from the SSH domain and beyond, and to reinforce the visibility and impact of the role of the thematic clusters at large. Some of them will be summarised in the subsections to follow. In addition several documents and templates have been drafted that will play a supporting role in the post-project promotion, maintenance and/or governance of the project results. This includes material for branding, financial commitments and procedures for quality monitoring. The remainder of the section will highlight a.o. the exploitable results, the MoU, the SSH Open Marketplace.

Figure 2. SSHOC results highlights

2.2 Exploitable Results

2.2.1 33 KERs

In the context of WP2, an overview has been created of the key exploitable results (KERs), services that have been realised and/or updated in the context of the SSHOC project. They are listed in section 4 of the SSHOC Exploitation Plan¹⁰. See also Annex 1. These 33 KERs form a crucial basis for some of the activities to be undertaken in the post-project period to extend the service offer and to widen the outreach to potential communities of use. The responsibility for the maintenance of the services is primarily with the service providers, in most cases one of the ERICs involved in the consortium although voluntary contributions from others will be welcomed. As the ERICs are legal entities with a longer-term financial horizon, the commitment towards service maintenance has been ensured for the first post-project period.

The overview gives examples from each of the five KER categories distinguished:

- Data Management
- Datasets
- Processing & Analysis
- Sharing & Discovery
- Training & Support

2.2.2 SSHOC Open Marketplace

The KER overview also illustrates how all services are discoverable via the SSHOC Open Marketplace, the platform through which the SSH service offer can be explored and accessed¹¹. The SSHOC Open Marketplace is the main result of WP7. Apart from the platform implementation, the work also included the development of a model for the post-project governance, maintenance and content curation, agreed by three of the ERICs involved. SSHOC Deliverable 7.5 Marketplace - Governance¹², and Annex 2 to this document should be referred to for a summary of the **Terms of Reference (ToR) for the Governing Board** that have been agreed. The parties involved in this body have agreed on a financial

¹⁰ Marieke Willems, Stephanie Parker, Martina Drascic, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Franciska de Jong, Laure Barbot, Daan Broeder, Ariane Néroulidis, Diana Zavala Rojas, Nicolas Larrousse, Ricarda Braukmann, Mari Kleemola, Yuri Pettinicchi, Athina Kritsotaki, Holly Wright, Cees van der Eijk, Albin Ahmeti, Ami Saji, ... Amaury de Vicq. (2022). SSHOC Exploitation Plan (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034593>

¹¹ See <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/ssh-open-marketplace> (Accessed April 2022).

¹² Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Edward J. Gray, Laure Barbot, Arnaud Roi, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). D7.5 Marketplace - Governance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608487>

model to cover the costs (in cash and in kind) for sustaining the platform until the end of 2023. This agreement will be renewed in the course of 2023.

2.2.3 Services onboarded in EOSC Portal

Many of the thematic services resulting from SSHOC have been onboarded in the SSH Open Marketplace. This service discovery platform has been registered in the EOSC Portal¹³.

In addition the SSH RIs involved in SSHOC have registered some of the individual services developed or enhanced in the context of the SSHOC project directly in the EOSC Portal as well, and more registrations are to be expected. It should also be mentioned that several services rooted in work by SSH groups but without SSHOC funding have been registered, such as several resources for text and data mining (TDM). Among the SSHOC services that are currently discoverable through the EOSC Portal are the following:

- CLARIN Switchboard¹⁴
- CLARIN Virtual Collection Registry¹⁵
- European Social Survey as a service¹⁶
- Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry¹⁷
- Survey Codings¹⁸
- UDPipe from LINDAT¹⁹
- Verbal Aggression Analyser²⁰
- Web Panel Sample Service²¹

The added value of registering individual services in EOSC Portal is a topic that is still being debated across the various domains and providers in the RI landscape. Anyhow the onboarding in the EOSC

¹³ see: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/ssh-open-marketplace> (Accessed April 2022)

¹⁴ for CLARIN Switchboard see:

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/language-resource-switchboard?q=Language+Resource+Switchboard> (Accessed April 2022).

¹⁵ for CLARIN Virtual Collection Registry see:

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/virtual-collection-registry?q=Virtual+Collection+Registry> (Accessed April 2022)

¹⁶ for ESS Service: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/european-social-survey-ess-as-a-service> (Accessed April 2022)

¹⁷ for Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry see:

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/ethnic-and-migrant-minority-survey-registry> (Accessed April 2022)

¹⁸ For Survey Codings see: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/surveycodings-org> (Accessed April 2022)

¹⁹ For UDIPipe see:

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/udpipe-tool-for-lemmatization-morphological-analysis-pos-tagging-and-dependency-parsing-in-multiple-languages> (Accessed April 2022)

²⁰ for Verbal Aggression Analyser see:

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/verbal-aggression-analyser-va-analyser> (Accessed April 2022)

²¹ for Web Panel Sample Service see: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/wpss-for-ess/details> (Accessed April 2022)

Portal of SSH services underlines the commitment within the cluster to a sustainable and harmonised service provision.

2.3 Memorandum of Understanding

An MoU has been conceived to underpin the continued collaboration amongst the SSHOC beneficiaries and other SSH stakeholders. It has currently been signed by all five ERICs involved in SSHOC²². The other project partners have been invited to join the SSH Open Cluster and to sign the MoU as well, and thus show the intent of participating in future activities to be conducted by the SSH Open Cluster.

The MoU has been carefully crafted to enable different types of collaboration and levels of involvement dependent on the topic in question. The MoU will support collaboration with regard to the representation of the SSH vis-à-vis EOSC and EOSC projects, but, importantly, it will also provide a framework for common service provisioning. The maintenance of the SSH Open Marketplace as a common service platform of the SSH Open Cluster is the most salient element of the post-project collaboration outlined in the MoU. In addition, the agreement will also provide the formal context for other common services and activities, such as the SSH Vocabulary Commons, or services with a common curation aspect. Continued common curation is considered to be a particularly important precondition for the sustainability of many project results.

The parties who have signed the MoU aim to further unlock the innovation potential of the cluster, maximise the societal and economic benefits from the investments in the SSH RIs, and thereby contribute to enhanced sustainability conditions for them. A sustainable brand around the SSH Open Cluster, Research Resources for the Social Sciences and Humanities, supports and visualises the continued collaboration. The various types of expertise and networks developed in SSHOC will continue to support the further shaping of the SSH Cluster and EOSC through the participation of many people from the SSHOC community in EOSC task forces and projects.

The MoU is not legally binding, but it is an umbrella agreement that shows existing intent to continue the collaboration, and may attract the interest in collaboration of new signatories. For specific results stemming from the continued collaboration, more detailed and in some cases legally binding agreements, SLAs and similar will be used, with reference to the umbrella MoU.

2.4 Future Surveys: Potential Topics

The understanding among the key representatives of the various parties and communities involved in SSHOC about the context in which the project results could or should be sustained has gradually evolved. The increased understanding of the SSHOC value proposition goes hand in hand with the

²² Press release on the signing of the MoU:

<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-signs-mou-bolster-cloud-services-social-science-and-humanities> (Accessed April 2022)

articulation and appreciation of the value proposition of EOSC, the specific role for thematic services in EOSC and the model of services onboarding in EOSC. Gradually the community is becoming more knowledgeable and is getting ready for a critical role in the provision of feedback on how the landscape is taking shape. For instance, awareness is growing that the thematic services from communities can also be useful for neighbouring communities outside the native cluster, and thus invite central (EOSC-level) coordination or other inter-cluster agreements. In the first year(s) after the SSHOC project, one or more surveys based on selections from the topic list included as Annex 3 might bring new and updated insights into the community support both from within the SSH domain and from other relevant communities and stakeholders.

Home Lineup Pings Hey! Activity My Stuff Find

SSHOC Consortium › Message Board

ANNOUNCEMENT

Memorandum of Understanding for the establishment of the SSH Open Cluster - instructions for signing

Martina Drascic Capar · Apr 22 · Notified 293 people

Dear partners,

as announced in March and shared during the SSHOC Final Conference, **all five SSH ERICs have signed the SSHOC Memorandum of Understanding!**

5 ERICs signed.png · 2.24 MB · [View full-size](#) · [Download](#)

The Memorandum:

As you already know, the MoU deals with the following broad areas of common interest: support to the SSH research communities, optimised use of existing resources, identification and response to challenges, visibility and branding in the area of SSH, high-level interactions with the EC and other EU bodies, advocate SSH research community interests in European and international research context, single contact point in collaboration with European and global scientific organisations, and finally, visibility, impact, and sustainability of the SSH domain and its stakeholders with coordinated representation to the general public, national governments, non-EU countries and global players

Figure 3. Following the public invitation for partners to join the MoU, a first round of signing took place in the context of the Final Conference in Brussels (6-7 April 2022). Instructions and invitation for signing the MoU were shared with all project partners on SSHOC Basecamp.

3. Roadmap

3.1 Actions/Tasks

3.1.1 Coordinated ongoing tasks

- Communication of the SSHOC value proposition
- Involvement of infrastructural initiatives and ESFRI projects in SSH that are interested in joining the MoU for the SSH Open Cluster.
- SSH Open Marketplace: operation and maintenance
- Support joint visibility and branding in the area of SSH
- Coordination of inter-cluster activities
- Coordination of activities towards key common stakeholders including EU institutions (European Commission, Council, Parliament, Committee of the Regions), EOSC Association, ESFRI, national ministries, funding bodies, user communities, international partnerships, regulatory authorities, and industry.
- Collaboration in EU funded proposals and projects targeting joint strategic goals and interests and/or with a specific role for science clusters.
- Engagement with relevant networks of experts.

3.1.3 Specific tasks

- Drafting Rules of Procedure to ensure transparency in decision taking at the cluster-level, clarity on the topics for which a joint voice of the SSH Open Cluster is endorsed by all, and a model for rotating representation.
- Establishing a liaison between the SSH Open Cluster and EOSC-A, aligned with the emerging model for communication between the existing clusters and EOSC-A to ensure an effective exchange and visibility of the science-rooted non-national initiatives such as the clusters, and the other pillars of the EOSC landscape.
- Promoting the actions from emerging inter-cluster cooperation activities.
- Providing a template for Service Level Agreements (SLA) that regulate the commitments between two parties in relation to service provision or joint service development.

- Promoting the guidelines developed for some of the KERs with a potential for community-wide impact, such as those for the development and depositing of FAIR training materials, the GDPR guidelines for SSH, Guidelines for building survey-specific corpora, and the Code of Conduct.
- Consolidation of the support for repository certification and other quality assurance measures in line with the results of T8.2.
- Coordination of a common agenda for SSH Vocabulary Commons, an initiative rooted in SSHOC work package WP3, that is envisaged to transcend the duration of the SSHOC project and that will be endorsed and supported by the SSH Open Cluster. The activities will align with the SSH Vocabulary Commons Charter (see Annex 4), and have a particular focus on:
 - Collaboration with platform developers such as Skosmos²³
 - Hosting SSH-specific vocabulary services (based on a best-effort model, or SLAs depending on the interest/need of specific organisations).
- Onboarding Citizen Science initiatives based on the insights discussed in the SSHOC workshop²⁴ on this topic of June 2021 organised by LIBER.

3.1.3 Tasks for individual RIs

- Maintenance of information pages on the relationship of the individual RIs, SSHOC and EOSC for each RI, e.g.²⁵
- Collection and promotion of use cases for thematic services and workflows, in part through common publication channels and aligned formats
- Onboarding of thematic services to the EOSC service catalogue
- Enhancement of existing training programmes²⁶.

3.2 Timeline

The timeline for the actions lines listed in section 3.1 and visualised below is indicative only, with just a few dependencies that have to be reckoned with:

²³ See: <https://skosmos.org> (Accessed April 2022)

²⁴ See workshop here:

<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-liber-2021-conference-onboarding-citizen-science-and-role-research-libraries-barriers> (Accessed April 2022)

²⁵ CLARIN: <https://www.clarin.eu/eosc>; DARIAH: <https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/1060>; CEESDA: <https://ceesda.eu/Development-Impact/> (Accessed April 2022)

²⁶ for an overview of the currently available materials: <https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-training-discovery-toolkit> (Accessed April 2022)

- The continued interest of the other cluster initiatives to maintain a model for inter-cluster communication and collaboration
- The continued commitment of the parties the SSH RI landscape which have undersigned the MoU or plan to do so, towards to goals expressed and the intent to provide the required resources and capacity.

Figure 4. Draft timeline of actions

4. Concluding Remarks

The sustainability of the SSHOC project results and the post-project collaboration under the header of SSH Open Cluster will critically depend on the commitment of the parties involved and the availability of resources to keep the tools and resources offered operational and accessible, to continue the outreach and educational action lines in the post-project stage, and to remain visible and organised as a science cluster in the RI landscape with a clear and common understanding of the model of representation and communication on behalf of the cluster.

SSHOC is the first EOSC cluster project reaching the end of the project stage, and it has been able to engage policy makers both from EU bodies and national institutions, the other science clusters, and representatives of the EOSC-Association. The discussions with all of these parties about the models and conditions required for a lasting existence, the instruments for growing uptake and the steps towards increasing impact in the domain of SSH and beyond will continue to be on the agenda. And as underlined also in the SSHOC Legacy Booklet, the user-friendly SSH data hub that has been realised marks a fundamental step in building the EOSC that can serve as an example for other initiatives aiming at integrating a thematic service offer. In particular for any attempt to provide support for the kind of diverse range of disciplines and methodological frameworks coming together in SSH, as well as for the truly multidisciplinary agendas in which SSH researchers are involved. As the EOSC landscape will evolve, the division of roles and responsibilities of the various European, national and local stakeholders will become more articulate and suitable models for resourcing²⁷ (in cash or in kind) the next stage in the life cycle of EOSC cluster initiatives will undoubtedly be discussed in more detail. The quality of SSH Open Cluster services and the user satisfaction will be even more critical for the potential of the SSH Open Cluster to advance the SSH domain, and to guide it through the digital transformation and implementation of the Open Science agenda. The parties who signed the SSH Open Cluster MoU all see the importance of a strong and lasting commitment towards these objectives and the roadmap presented here will serve as their compass.

²⁷ In the context of EOSC the use of the term 'resourcing models' is often preferred over the term 'business model', to avoid the interpretation that a 'for profit' approach is in the scope of EOSC. (Cf. the work plan for the Horizon Europe project EOSC Focus (June 2022 - June 2025). Regarding fee-based models for the use of EOSC services, the common understanding is that any payment for services are to be arranged through institutional arrangements, rather than models that come with a fee per use.

5. References

Publications:

- SSHOC Consortium (2022). SSHOC Legacy booklet. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6394462>
- Marieke Willems, Stephanie Parker, Martina Drascic, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Franciska de Jong, Laure Barbot, Daan Broeder, Ariane Néroulidis, Diana Zavala Rojas, Nicolas Larrousse, Ricarda Braukmann, Mari Kleemola, Yuri Pettinicchi, Athina Kritsotaki, Holly Wright, Cees van der Eijk, Albin Ahmeti, Ami Saji, ... Amaury de Vicq. (2022). SSHOC Exploitation Plan (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034593>
- Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Edward J. Gray, Laure Barbot, Arnaud Roi, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). D7.5 Marketplace - Governance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608487>
- Marieke Willems, Stephanie Parker, Martina Drascic, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Franciska de Jong, Laure Barbot, Daan Broeder, Ariane Néroulidis, Diana Zavala Rojas, Nicolas Larrousse, Ricarda Braukmann, Mari Kleemola, Yuri Pettinicchi, Athina Kritsotaki, Holly Wright, Cees van der Eijk, Albin Ahmeti, Ami Saji, ... Amaury de Vicq. (2022). SSHOC Exploitation Plan (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034593>
- Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Edward J. Gray, Laure Barbot, Arnaud Roi, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). D7.5 Marketplace - Governance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608487>

Web resources:

- Making Science Happen. ESFRI White Paper 2020; link: https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/White_paper_ESFRI-final.pdf (accessed April 2022)
- Supporting the Transformative Impact of Research Infrastructures on European Research (HLEG report 2020); link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/supporting-transformative-impact-research-infrastructures-european-research_en (Accessed April 2022)
- How ERICs Contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals; link: <https://www.eric-forum.eu/2021/10/11/erics-contribution-to-the-un-sustainable-development-goals-sdgs/> (Accessed April 2022)
- ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement, June 2021; link: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-science-clusters-position-statement-expectations-and-long-term-commitment-open-science> (Accessed April 2022)
- Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC. A FAIR Lady report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group; link: <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/solutions-sustainable-eosc-fair-lady-report> (Accessed April 2022)

- Assessment on the Implementation of the ERIC Regulation (draft 31/08/2021); link:
<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/cdbe5c78-353b-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> (Accessed April 2022)
- European Research Area Policy Agenda (2022 – 2024); November 2021;
link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/files/european-research-area-policy-agenda-2022-2024_en
(Accessed April 2022)
- Research infrastructures look to renew their role in new-look European Research Area. In: Science | Business; published 22 July 2021; link:
<https://sciencebusiness.net/news/research-infrastructures-look-renew-their-role-new-look-european-research-area> (Accessed April 2022)
- SSH Open Marketplace: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/ssh-open-marketplace> (Accessed April 2022).
- CLARIN Switchboard:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/language-resource-switchboard?q=Language+Resource+Switchboard> (Accessed April 2022).
- CLARIN Virtual Collection Registry:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/virtual-collection-registry?q=Virtual+Collection+Registry> (Accessed April 2022)
- ESS Service: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/european-social-survey-ess-as-a-service>
(Accessed April 2022)
- Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/ethnic-and-migrant-minority-survey-registry>
(Accessed April 2022)
- Survey Codings: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/surveycodings-org> (Accessed April 2022)
- UDIPipe:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/udpipe-tool-for-lemmatization-morphological-analysis-pos-tagging-and-dependency-parsing-in-multiple-languages> (Accessed April 2022)
- Verbal Aggression Analyser:
<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/verbal-aggression-analyser-va-analyser> (Accessed April 2022)
- Web Panel Sample Service: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/wpss-for-ess/details> (Accessed April 2022)
- Press release on the signing of the MoU:
<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-signs-mou-bolster-cloud-services-social-science-and-humanities> (Accessed April 2022)
- Skosmos: <https://skosmos.org> (Accessed April 2022)
- SSHOC at LIBER 2021 Conference - Onboarding Citizen Science and the role of research libraries: barriers and accelerators:
<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-liber-2021-conference-onboarding-citizen-science-and-role-research-libraries-barriers> (Accessed April 2022)
- CLARIN website on EOSC: <https://www.clarin.eu/eosc> (Accessed April 2022)

DARIAH website on EOSC: <https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/1060> (Accessed April 2022)

CESSDA website on EOSC: <https://cessda.eu/Development-Impact/> (Accessed April 2022)

Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-training-discovery-toolkit> (Accessed April 2022)

SSHOC Stakeholder: <https://sshopencloud.eu/stakeholders> (accessed April 2022)

Annex 1 - 33 Key Exploitable Results

Overview of Key Exploitable Results. (See for details section 4 of the SSHOC Exploitation Plan²⁸).

33 SSHOCing Key Exploitable Results to support your research in SSH and Beyond

²⁸ Marieke Willems, Stephanie Parker, Martina Drascic, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Franciska de Jong, Laure Barbot, Daan Broeder, Ariane Néroulidis, Diana Zavala Rojas, Nicolas Larrousse, Ricarda Braukmann, Mari Kleemola, Yuri Pettinicchi, Athina Kritsotaki, Holly Wright, Cees van der Eijk, Albin Ahmeti, Ami Saji, ... Amaury de Vicq. (2022). SSHOC Exploitation Plan (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034593>

Annex 2 - ToR Governing Board SSH Open Marketplace

The text below contains the Terms of Reference (ToR) of the Governing Board of the SSH Open Marketplace. It is copied from D7.5 Marketplace - Governance²⁹, pages 14-16.

The Governing Board

The Governing Board is committed to support the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace. It acts as its ultimate decision-making authority. The SSH Open Marketplace was launched only recently and further development and evaluations could modify and/or add up more responsibilities to this body.

MISSIONS

The Governing Board defines the Marketplace strategic policy with regards to scientific, technical and managerial matters.

With regards to scientific matters:

- The Governing Board defines and decides on the scientific orientation of the Marketplace. The scientific orientation is defined here as the orientation chosen to foster the offer and effectiveness with regards to SSH research's needs and challenges.
- The scientific orientation's decisions, when related to core editorial aspects, are taken alongside the Editorial Board, especially when those relate to editorial choices.
- Any recommendation or demand for action from the Editorial Board, regarding editorial policies (addition, modification, deletion) shall be approved by the Governing Board.
- In the light of the Marketplace strategic scientific orientation, the Governing Board should work to ensure the best alignment conceivable between the EOSC and the SSH Open Marketplace. For this aim, the body has to maintain contact with relevant actors from SSHOC and EOSC.

With regards to technical matters:

- The Governing Board approves the decisions of the Editorial Board. If any conflict arises from different approaches, then the Governing Board decides.
- Any recommendation or demand for action from the Editorial Board, editing the technical policy (addition, modification, deletion) shall be approved by the Governing Board.

With regards to managerial matters:

²⁹ Clara Petitfils, Suzanne Dumouchel, Nicolas Larrousse, Edward J. Gray, Laure Barbot, Arnaud Roi, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Stefan Buddenbohm, & Tomasz Parkola. (2021). D7.5 Marketplace - Governance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608487>

- The Governing Board defines the annual budget and the work plan - The SSH Open Marketplace Strategic work plan - which is regularly updated to pursue the agile methodology adopted so far for the implementation of the Marketplace.
- Any recommendation or demand for action from the Editorial Board, editing the strategic orientation (addition, modification, deletion) shall be approved by the Governing Board.
- The above-mentioned administrative components should be made after consulting the Editorial Board, but also when deemed necessary, the Contributors Community, to understand their needs and expectations.
- The above-mentioned administrative components should be agreed based on the mechanism for decision taking for decision taking suggested below.
- The Governing Board oversees and directs the work undertaken in the other body, the Editorial Board, but also in the Contributors Community.

COMPOSITION

The Governing Board is composed of representatives of the contributing partner ERICs. “Contributing partners” can be defined as partners that financially contribute to the sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace.

This representation will be organised as follow:

- The Governing Board is composed of one representative per ERIC, independently from each contribution. The body will therefore count five members - at least for the first year after the SSHOC project’s end.
- Each contributing ERIC appoints its own representative for the Marketplace’s Governing Board.
- This body should gather twice a year. This pace should be tested during the first year of this governance scheme’s implementation. Later, if a different scheduling is required and preferred by representatives, another model will be adopted.

The decision-making process will be organised as follow:

- As the group is rather small, consensus should be the first decision-making process adopted.
- If the consensus is not reached, then a voting system is required and a fair and well-balanced process should be ensured. The following mechanism is therefore suggested :
 - To consider the possibility that an ERIC could contribute more than others, a voting based on the financial contribution’s proportionality can be considered.
 - However, to avoid a potential “voting monopoly” based solely on the financial weight, the voting should, in addition, gather at least the majority of representatives (thus three out of five members).
- The decision-making process is agreed in the agreement signed by the GB members and should be modified by unanimity.

RELATIONS TO OTHER BODIES

As described above, the Governing Board determines the Marketplace's strategic orientation and policies on scientific, technical and managerial matters. Regarding all three fields, whether the consensus or the proportionality voting mechanism is chosen as the decision-making process the Governing Board shall always consult the other body and take its recommendations into account. For instance, the Editorial Board, involved in the daily operation of the Marketplace will be able to provide frequent and operational-related inputs to the Governing Board. It should also consider the Contributors Community's needs, challenges and expectations.

Annex 3 - Potential Survey Topic List

An overview of potential topics/questions that could be used in future surveys about the SSHOC value proposition and the position of the SSH Open Cluster in the wider RI landscape.

1. SSHOC Value Proposition
 - a. What do you think of the current SSHOC value proposition³⁰ in terms of stakeholder focus, feasibility, affordability, etc.?
 - b. In the context of SSHOC, which governance elements do you see as relevant to the sustainability of the project value proposition? (Formal model (such as MoU) for sustained collaboration at the level of the SSH cluster, extending the cluster to new SSH projects on the ESFRI Roadmap, involvement of non-RI nodes, etc.)

2. EOSC ecosystem /federated service offer
 - a. Which initiatives/liaisons/projects related to EOSC do you consider as crucial for sustainability of the SSHOC results beyond the funding lifecycle?
 - b. How do you see the role of national infrastructures in the sustainability of the SSHOC results beyond the funding lifecycle?
 - c. What do you see as the key conditions for delivering a contribution to the SSH Open Marketplace/EOSC service offer after the end of the SSHOC project and/or within a year after its funding cycle? (Budget, human resources, platform interoperability, TRL of service before onboarding, etc.)
 - d. What impact do you expect from offering services through an SSH platform for the uptake of the services your RI/institute have been working in the context of SSHOC?
 - e. What can we learn about sustainability prerequisites from the distributed ERICs?

3. Societal impact
 - a. Which societal sectors do you anticipate will benefit from the SSHOC results and the service offer as visible in the SSH Open Marketplace and the EOSC Portal, and/or the continued collaboration at the level of the cluster?
 - b. Organisations from which sectors should be considered as crucial allies/representatives application domains?
 - c. Do you know of any organisations beyond the non-profit domain that should be informed about the SSHOC results?

4. Internationalisation
 - a. Do you see added value in alignment of the RI collaboration in SSH beyond Europe? For which regions/continents?

³⁰See stakeholders here: <https://sshopencloud.eu/stakeholders> (accessed April 2022)

- b. Which organisations should be considered as crucial allies for further enhanced international positioning?
- 5. General/other
 - a. Do you have any specific recommendations to make about SSHOC/SSH-RI sustainability?
 - b. Under which conditions/until when would your organisation want to stay involved in this discussion? (until Q3 2022, end-of-project + 1 year, other)

Annex 4 - SSH Vocabulary Commons Charter

Daan Broeder, Mari Kleemola, Herve L'Hours

October 2021

The SSH Vocabulary Commons brings together experts and managers from SSH research infrastructures CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH and E-RIHS that agree to share their expertise and work towards common recommendations for firstly, using and managing vocabularies used in SSH and secondly operating, sharing and managing of vocabulary services useful for the broad SSH community.

The SSH Vocabulary Commons work is specifically directed towards:

- Common recommendations for creating, managing and using vocabularies used in SSH research and resource management that will make the SSH infrastructures better interoperable and more efficient.
- Aligning current vocabulary management practices with EOSC and FAIR principles making vocabularies first-class citizens, easy to find, share and access.
- Improving facilities for multilingual vocabularies.
- Promoting sharing of vocabularies and management procedures and software between different SSH domains and organisations by recommending specific Knowledge Organisation/Representation language formats e.g. SKOS and how to apply these e.g. vocabulary metadata, versioning
- Providing easier cross domain integration of (meta)data and semantic interoperability by supporting and providing procedures for vocabulary matching
- Maintaining contacts with vocabulary software development teams and promote SSH infrastructure interests
- Facilitating vocabulary recommendation, supporting researchers finding relevant vocabulary for their research.
- Providing a default vocabulary hosting and publishing service for orphaned vocabularies

The SSH Vocabulary Commons starts as an initiative from the SSHOC project and is supported by activities of several SSHOC tasks in SSHOC WP3, but is planned and organised to transcend the duration of the SSHOC project and continue as an endorsed activity supported by the SSH Open Cluster collaboration.

The members of the SSH Vocabulary Commons will meet and consult regularly, discuss priorities and actions to achieve the stated goals. The Vocabulary Commons will maintain a mailing list, and document repository for communication. The Vocabulary Commons membership is desired to be a fair representation from all the major EU SSH infrastructures that actively work on issues concerning vocabulary use and management. Although the documents are public, new members are added to the list by co-optation and are expected to actively contribute.